

Teacher's Pedagogical Competence, Teaching Commitment, and Work Performance: A Basis For An Intervention Plan

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Abstract

This study assessed the pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance of Key Stage 1 and 2 teachers in Enrile East District and examined their relationships with selected profile variables. Specifically, it sought to describe the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, years of teaching, and civil status; determine the level of their pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance; test the relationships among these variables and their profiles; investigate the mediating role of teaching commitment between competence and performance; identify issues and concerns encountered by teachers; and propose an intervention plan. The study employed a descriptive–correlational design with seventy-four (74) teachers as respondents, utilizing survey questionnaires and statistical tools such as weighted mean, Chi-Square, Cramer's V, and mediation analysis.

Findings revealed that most respondents were female, married, and highly experienced, with more than ten years in service. Teachers demonstrated high pedagogical competence in evaluation of learning, managing student behavior, use of ICT, and lecturer–student interaction. They also showed strong teaching commitment to students, teaching, and school, but only moderate commitment to the profession. Teaching performance was consistently high across instructional, professional, and personal qualities. Statistical analyses revealed no significant relationships between teachers' profile variables and their competence, commitment, or performance, suggesting that these qualities are shaped more by professional and institutional factors than by demographics. Mediation analysis showed that teaching commitment did not significantly mediate the relationship between competence and performance, while pedagogical competence exerted a strong direct effect on performance.

Despite these strengths, teachers identified issues such as limited instructional resources, classroom management difficulties, curriculum demands, workload pressures, lack of technological support, limited professional development opportunities, and stress-related concerns. In response, the study proposed TEACH-UP: A Strategic Intervention Plan to address these concerns through resource mobilization, inclusive teaching strategies, classroom management support, workload reduction, continuous professional development, and institutional recognition.

The study concludes that pedagogical competence is the most decisive factor influencing teaching performance, while commitment enhances motivation but does not significantly mediate outcomes. It recommends targeted capacity-building initiatives, improved ICT integration, strengthened teacher motivation and retention strategies, systemic support for resource and workload challenges, and the implementation of TEACH-UP to sustain and enhance teacher effectiveness in the Enrile East District.

Keywords: *pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, work performance, teacher profiles, mediation analysis, TEACH-UP intervention, Enrile East District*

Introduction

Teaching is the backbone of the development of people and society. As with many countries across the world, the educational standards in a country depend on the pedagogical skills of teachers, their commitment to the profession, and their overall work performance. Studies conducted by global bodies such as the OECD and UNESCO emphasize the perennial relationship between teacher effectiveness and student results. Finland, Singapore, and South Korea have pioneered benchmarks in educational standards attainment with their rigorous preparation of teachers, continuing education, and multifaceted evaluations.

In the Philippine context, efforts like the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) seek to focus more on improving educational needs, but gaps still remain, particularly in outlying rural communities. The K to 12 curriculums, together with other reform policies set out, has a basis for a more progressive product, but conditions such as lack of materials, inadequate training, and inconsistent implementation of policies (DepEd, 2013) remain deep-seated issues.

The present study is also aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 4: Quality Education, which aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. SDG 4 emphasizes the importance of qualified and competent teachers as a key driver of improving educational outcomes. Specifically, Target 4.c highlights the need to substantially increase the supply of qualified teachers through international cooperation for teacher training and professional development, especially in developing countries. In this context, strengthening teachers' pedagogical competence, enhancing their teaching commitment, and improving their work performance directly contribute to achieving quality education. For districts such as Enrile East, where teachers face challenges related to limited resources, professional development opportunities, and technological support, addressing these concerns becomes essential in fulfilling SDG 4 objectives. By assessing teachers' competencies and proposing an intervention plan, this study supports efforts to enhance instructional quality, promote teacher effectiveness, and ultimately improve learning outcomes, thereby contributing to the broader global agenda of sustainable and inclusive education.

In the case of the municipality of Enrile East District, there are learners studying in schools that portray most of the challenges articulated in a broader context of national challenges. Many teachers in this district face challenges such as inadequate instructional materials, limited professional advancement, and low levels of technology within the district. These challenges serve as obstacles in the utilization of modern and constructive techniques of teaching and learning, as witnessed during the most recently conducted defense session.

Teacher commitment and work performance have a direct role in the productivity of education systems. There is evidence that professional dedication positively correlates with student outcomes and engagement levels (Santos, 2020; Madigan & Kim, 2021). Throughout Enrile East District, the defense discussion showed that the majority of teachers' morale and engagement were affected by their workload, resources at hand, and the level of community support.

Teaching performance is impacted by several elements, including but not limited to classroom management, the delivery of instruction, and the application of creative methods (Raducu & Stanculescu, 2022). In Enrile East District, teachers face several challenges, such as the lack of teaching aids, inadequate staff training opportunities, and the challenge of overpopulated classrooms. It was also noted that there was a lack of adequate training and administrative assistance, which worked counter to these problems. Access to resources and continuing professional development opportunities substantially enhance a teacher's output (De Villa & Manalo, 2020; Wang, 2022).

This study aimed primarily to evaluate the pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and overall performance of Key Stage 1 and 2 teachers in Enrile East District. The results inform the creation of an intervention plan to resolve the issues and improve the quality of education. The intervention is focused on providing adequate in-service training, mentoring, and the necessary resources, especially ICT, to foster teachers' professional development.

Teachers, school administrators, policymakers, and the education sector as a whole will greatly benefit from this study. With its insights into teacher effectiveness and competence, this research is helpful in formulating policy changes and resource distribution. It seeks to aid the Department of Education (DepEd) in program development that serves the needs of teachers in rural areas while meeting international standards and best practices (DepEd, 2013; OECD, 2018).

The study looked at the specific case of East District and focuses on teachers, specifically considering their self-evaluated instructional skills, teaching willingness, and job productivity. Teachers from other districts and private institutions are not considered. Its purpose is to offer context-relevant solutions to issues at hand and guide highly specific, context-driven action without the pretense of broader applicability beyond the study's context.

This results of this are anticipated to add value to policies regarding teacher training and the evaluation of teacher performance. Information collected for this study may assist the Department of Education in addressing competency gaps, especially in rural districts such as Enrile East. The study may also assist school administrators in better designing some support mechanisms for teachers.

Thus, the study sought to propose practical solutions to issues related to teacher training, instructional practices, and assessment of performance. It proposes an intervention plan based on the data collected through the study to improve teachers' Integration of technology, professional growth, and long-term commitment toward school improvement.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to assess the teachers' pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance in Enrile East District for the School Year 2025-2026, as a basis for an intervention plan.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Civil Status
 - 1.4 Years of Service
2. What is the level of teachers' pedagogical competence as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 Evaluation of Learning
 - 2.2 Managing Student Behavior During Lecture
 - 2.3 Using ICT to Enhance Learning
 - 2.4 Lecturers' Student Interaction
3. What is the level of teachers' teaching commitment as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1 Commitment to Students
 - 3.2 Commitment to Teaching
 - 3.3 Commitment to School
 - 3.4 Commitment to Profession
4. What is the teachers' work performance as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of:
 - 4.1 Instructional
 - 4.2 Professional
 - 4.3 Personal
5. Is there a significant relationship on the level of teachers' pedagogical competence as assessed by the two groups of respondents and their profile variables?
6. Is there a significant relationship on the level of teachers' teaching commitment as assessed by the two groups of respondents and their profile variables?
7. Is there a significant relationship on teachers' work performance as assessed by the two groups of respondents and their profile variables?
8. To what extent does teaching commitment mediate the relationship between teachers' pedagogical competence, and work performance?
9. What are the issues and concerns encountered by the respondents alongside their pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance?
10. What intervention plan can be proposed to address issues and concerns encountered by the respondents alongside their pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance?

METHODS AND PROCEDURES

Research Design

The study employed descriptive–correlational research design to assess the teachers’ pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance among Key Stage 1 and Key Stage 2 teachers in the Enrile East District for the School Year 2025–2026.

Teachers’ profile, pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance possessed by the teachers were descriptively analyzed using a thorough quantitative approach. This analysis and method served to highlight the instructional efficacy, motivation, and professional involvement of the teachers. The primary focus of the study included the correlations between the pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance of teachers to their profile variables. Moreover, the issues and concerns encountered by the teachers, a descriptive survey design was employed. This design allowed the researcher to collect data through structured questionnaires and open-ended responses in order to determine the challenges related to pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance. The results of SOP 9 served as the basis for proposing an intervention plan.

Respondents of the Study

This research involved two respondent groups: Public elementary teachers in Key Stage 1 and Key Stage 2 in the Enrile East District for the school year 2025-2026 using total enumeration sampling, which guaranteed that every teacher who is qualified in the designated schools took part in the study. This approach is suitable as it achieved full coverage of the intended study population, which, in turn, reduces sampling errors.

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents of the Study

School	No. of Key Stage 1 Teachers	No. of Key Stage 2 Teacher
Lanna Elementary School	5	5
Enrile East Central School (Magalalag)	7	8
Alibago Elementary School	6	5
Marracuru Elementary School	3	3
Inga Elementary School	4	4
Lemu Elementary School	5	5
Divisoria Elementary School	4	5
Don Jose Paulino Elementary School	2	3
Total:	36	38

To ensure that there is no bias in capturing the entire population of teachers in the Enrile East District, both Key Stage 1 and Key Stage 2 teachers were included and treated as a single group of respondents in the analysis. Grouping these respondents as one enhances the comprehensive diagnosis of pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work

performance across the elementary level. This approach allows the study to generate a unified assessment of teachers' competencies and performance regardless of key stage classification.

Data Gathering Tool

The study utilized standardized pedagogical instruments to measure the teachers' pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance among Key Stage 1 and Key Stage 2 teachers in the Enrile East District. Each instrument was selected based on its accuracy, reliability, and relevance to the variables of the research problem.

The Pedagogical Competence Assessment Tool, adapted from Shulman (1987), was used to measure teachers' skills in planning and organizing teaching and learning activities, including instructional delivery and assessment strategies. This instrument consisted of Likert-scale statements covering mastery of content, instructional strategies, assessment techniques, and student engagement, with modifications to suit contemporary educational settings in the Philippines.

To measure teaching commitment, the Teaching Commitment Scale adapted from Meyer and Allen (1991) was employed. This tool assessed teachers' commitment to students, teaching, school, and profession, capturing both cognitive and emotional aspects of commitment. The instrument utilized a five-point Likert scale where respondents indicated their level of agreement with statements reflecting their motivation and dedication to teaching.

Teachers' work performance was measured using the Work Performance Evaluation Checklist derived from the Department of Education's Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS, 2019). This checklist evaluated teachers' effectiveness in lesson planning, instructional delivery, and assessment of learning. The evaluation followed DepEd's key performance indicators, ensuring that teacher productivity was measured in alignment with national competency standards.

Additionally, a researcher-developed instrument was used to identify the issues and concerns encountered by teachers, particularly for Statement of the Problem 9. This tool included both open-ended and Likert-scale questions designed to determine barriers related to pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance.

Prior to its administration, the instrument underwent content validation by education experts to ensure clarity, objectivity, and content validity. The validated instrument served as the basis for identifying challenges faced by teachers and for developing the proposed intervention plan.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection adhered to ethical practices and was conducted upon approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB), ensuring compliance with ethical principles for research involving human participants. Prior to data gathering, an ethical review of the study was conducted, and the recommendations of the panel were incorporated before submission to the

adviser and the Dean of the Graduate School. The IRB evaluated the study's methodology, ethical considerations, and possible risks to participants. Data collection commenced only after the necessary ethics clearance was granted.

Following IRB approval, a formal request letter was submitted to the Department of Education (DepEd) – Enrile East District Office to seek permission to conduct the study. Upon approval, letters were also forwarded to the school heads of participating public elementary schools to secure authorization for the participation of Key Stage 1 and Key Stage 2 teachers. After obtaining permissions, an orientation and informed consent process was conducted with the respondents. During the orientation, the participants were informed about the purpose and scope of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, confidentiality and anonymity of responses, and their right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequences.

The research instruments were then administered to the respondents. The Pedagogical Competence Assessment Tool, Teaching Commitment Scale, and Work Performance Evaluation Checklist were accomplished by the teachers. The assessment of teachers' work performance was conducted collaboratively with school administrators to ensure objectivity. In addition, teachers were provided with the researcher-developed instrument designed to identify issues and concerns related to pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance for Statement of the Problem 9.

After the administration of the instruments, the accomplished questionnaires were retrieved on scheduled dates. The collected data were screened for completeness and accuracy. Responses that were incomplete or unclear were returned to the respondents for clarification to ensure reliability of the data. Once validated, the data were encoded, processed, and analyzed using appropriate statistical methods. The results were then interpreted in accordance with the objectives of the study, focusing on identifying trends, relationships, and key findings relevant to teachers' pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance.

Statistical Tools

The data gathered in this study were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to address each statement of the problem. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to determine the respondents' profile, assess the levels of pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance, examine relationships among variables, identify issues and concerns, and test the mediating effect of teaching commitment. The independent variable in the study is teachers' pedagogical competence, the dependent variable is teachers' work performance, and the mediating variable is teaching commitment.

Frequency and percentage were used to describe the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, plantilla position, years of service, number of relevant learning and development activities attended, and key stage.

The weighted mean was used to determine the level of teachers' pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance. The results were interpreted using a five-point Likert scale with the following range and descriptive equivalents: 4.50–5.00 (Very High), 3.50–4.49 (High), 2.50–3.49 (Moderate), 1.50–2.49 (Low), and 1.00–1.49 (Very Low). This scale

provided a uniform basis for interpreting the extent of competence, commitment, and performance among the respondents.

The Chi-square test of independence was employed to determine the significant relationships between teachers' pedagogical competence, teaching commitment, and work performance to their profile variables. To measure the strength of the association, Cramer's V was used.

Mediation analysis was applied to determine whether teaching commitment served as a mediating variable between pedagogical competence and work performance (SOP 8). This analysis examined whether pedagogical competence (independent variable) influences work performance (dependent variable) directly and indirectly through teaching commitment (mediating variable). The mediation analysis provided deeper insights into how teachers' commitment contributes to the relationship between competence and performance.

Lastly, frequency and rank were used to determine the issues and concerns encountered by the teachers alongside pedagogical competence, teaching commitment and work performance.

Summary of Findings

The following are the key findings of the study:

1. Profile of the Respondents
 - Majority of the respondents were in their middle adulthood, female, married, and highly experienced teachers with more than ten years of service.
2. Level of Teachers' Pedagogical Competence
 - Teachers demonstrated a high level of pedagogical competence, particularly in evaluation of learning, classroom management, and student interaction, while ICT integration obtained the lowest rating.
3. Level of Teaching Commitment
 - Teachers showed strong commitment to students, teaching, and school, but only moderate commitment to the profession.
4. Level of Teachers' Work Performance
 - Teachers exhibited a high level of work performance in instructional, professional, and personal qualities.
5. Correlation Between Teachers' Commitment and their Profile Variables
 - There was a significant relationship between teachers' age and pedagogical competence with respect to evaluation of learning and managing student behavior during lecture. Furthermore, years of teaching was significantly correlated as to lecturers' student interaction dimension.
6. Correlation Between Teachers' Work Engagement and their Profile Variables
 - There was a significant relationship between teachers' age and teaching commitment with respect to the school dimension. Also, years of teaching was significantly related to teaching commitment in terms of the school dimension.
7. There was a significant relationship between teachers' age and teaching commitment with respect to the school dimension. Also, years of teaching was significantly related to teaching commitment in terms of the school dimension.

- There was no significant relationship with age, sex, years of teaching, and civil status across the pedagogical competence, instructional, professional, and personal dimensions.
- 8. Extent of Teaching Commitment Mediate the Relationship Between Teachers' Pedagogical Competence and Work Performance
 - Pedagogical competence significantly influenced work performance, while teaching commitment did not significantly mediate the relationship.
- 9. Issues and Concerns Encountered by Teachers
 - Teachers identified issues such as limited instructional resources, classroom management difficulties, workload pressures, lack of technological support, and limited professional development opportunities.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, teachers in the Enrile East District possess high pedagogical competence, strong teaching commitment, and high work performance. However, challenges such as limited ICT integration, moderate professional commitment, and resource constraints affect sustained effectiveness. Pedagogical competence was found to be the strongest predictor of work performance. Addressing identified issues through structured intervention programs is necessary to sustain teacher effectiveness.

Recommendations

The study puts forward several recommendations grounded on the conclusions drawn from the findings. These recommendations are intended to address the identified issues, enhance teachers' pedagogical competence, strengthen their teaching commitment, and sustain high levels of work performance through targeted programs and institutional support. The following are humbly recommended:

1. School Heads and Master Teachers may implement mentoring and peer coaching programs to support less experienced teachers and sustain best instructional practices.
2. School Administrators and ICT Coordinators may provide ICT training, digital resources, and technical support to enhance technology integration in teaching.
3. DepEd District Supervisors may strengthen teacher motivation and retention programs through recognition, incentives, and career development opportunities.
4. School Heads and District Official may address resource shortages, classroom management challenges, and workload pressures by providing instructional materials and support mechanisms.
5. School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) Coordinators may implement the TEACH-UP Strategic Intervention Plan to enhance teachers' competence, commitment, and work performance.
6. Future researchers may conduct similar studies using additional variables such as leadership style, teacher well-being, and school climate, or expand the study to other districts to validate and compare findings.

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